

MIXING SYMBOLIC AND AUDIO DATA IN COMPUTER ASSISTED MUSIC ANALYSIS

A Case study from J. Harvey's *Speakings* (2008) for Orchestra and Live Electronics

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ABSTRACT

Starting from a (music) analytical question arising from the study of Jonathan Harvey's *Speakings* for orchestra and electronics (2008) we propose a computer-based approach in which score (symbolic) and recorded (audio) sources are considered in tandem. After extracting a set of relevant features we used machine-learning algorithms to explore how compositional and auditory dimensions articulate in defining the identity of certain sound-events appearing in the first movement of the composition and how they contribute to their similarity with events occurring in the second movement. The computer-assisted approach was used as basis for discussing the metaphor that inspired this particular piece, but has the potential to be extended to other compositions in the repertoire.

1. INTRODUCTION

A significant part of the orchestral music composed since the end of World War 2 has made extensive use of non-standard playing techniques, of microtonal tuning systems and/or elaborated complex "sound masses". The corresponding works have stretched the capacity of the written score to provide a complete mental "image" of a composition's overall sound to its limits. When orchestral and electro-acoustic sounds are superimposed in a single performance or, even more so, when they are intentionally seamlessly blended together, the gap between the written score and the sounding results may become even more acute. In the effort to analyze such compositions, the possibility to include and articulate information extracted from both the written score and the recording of its performance becomes a crucial issue.

Today's computer technology provides important resources that can be applied to tackle either audio or symbolic (MIDI) data. The transcription of a recorded performance into visual representations can serve as "proto-scores" that can be annotated and, if need be, aligned with a written score [1, 2]. MIR techniques permit to extract specific aspects of an audio file and have thus paved the way towards more differentiated perspectives on recorded sources [3, 4]. Comparable resources can also be found in the processing of written information. Specialized libraries exist that extract "statistical" fea-

tures, such as density or degrees of inharmonicity, from a MIDI file and retrace their evolutions in time [5]. Despite such resources, few examples can be found in the music analytical literature that explicitly seeks to articulate observations obtained from (and referable back to) the musical score and the recording of its performance.

In this article we present and discuss an example of such an attempt based on a (music) analytical question that arises from the study of Jonathan Harvey's *Speakings* for orchestra and electronics (2008).

This work cumulates both characteristics mentioned above. It makes extensive use of non-standard playing techniques deployed in complex textural structures and blends orchestral and electronic sounds together, at times in such a way as to make them indistinguishable from one another. When considering questions of identity and similarity between sound-events occurring in the piece, features extracted from both written and recorded sources bear, *a priori*, equal weight as a basis for investigation.

As it turns out, a wealth of information exists about this composition's genesis [6]. This has not only provided a basis for a preliminary analysis of the work but has also quite straightforwardly suggested questions of the type just mentioned. These, together with a brief description of Harvey's composition, will be presented in the first section of the present article.

How computer support was brought in, first to extract "global features" from the sound events considered and then to decide on how to classify and compare them within the context of our analysis, are the subjects of sections 3 and 4.

Although the questions underlying our discussion heavily rely on information provided by the composer – thus making them quite specific to the work at hand – the application of the suggested approach to a wider context should also be viable. This possibility will be the subject of the discussion provided in the closing section.

2. ABOUT J. HARVEY'S *SPEAKINGS*

2.1 Form and General Characteristics

Composed in 2008, *Speakings* is the result of collaboration between composer Jonathan Harvey and researchers at the IRCAM. As a byproduct of this collaboration, an article was published [6], describing some of the techno-

logical means applied to its realization (spatialization, real-time transformations, synchronization between orchestral and electronic sounds...).

From this source, we learn that: “*an evolution of speech consciousness [...], starting from baby screaming, cooing and babbling, through frenzied chatter to mantric serenity [provides] the basic metaphor of the half-hour work’s trajectory*”. As it turns out, this metaphor actually operates at two different levels.

First, as mentioned in the above quote, it provided an “abstract narrative” to the work’s overall three-movements structure (played without interruptions) of, respectively, 5’30, 14’00 and 8’30 durations. The first movement, dominated by the string instruments, occupies the lower dynamic range (up to *f*) and displays a darker and more “agitated” activity than the other two. The second movement involves more brass and woodwind instruments and progresses through an extended orchestral crescendo that culminates at *fff*. The last movement, finally, displays an overall calmer mood that mixes all the orchestral colors encountered during the previous two movements.

At a second level, the metaphor entered directly in the elaboration of some of the musical material appearing in the composition. In a way reminiscent to the *spectralist* approach, the composer used computer analyses of complex sounds to derive some of his material. The “*baby screaming, cooing and babbling,*” mentioned in the quote were obtained from recordings of actual baby sounds. As detailed in [6], these (the sounds, not the babies) were subjected to automatic transcription of speech signals into symbolic (melodic and harmonic) musical notation and the result transcribed to the orchestra so as to mimic the voice’s rhythm and natural inflections. In order to render the corresponding passages even more speech-like, a real-time transformation was applied during the performance to a selection of (solo) instruments within the orchestra. Another example of a similar procedure used a recording of the composer singing a short mantra. The corresponding “transcription” for orchestra enters gradually towards the end of the second movement and announces the “serenity” of the work’s concluding section.

The present analysis concentrates on the *baby sounds* that appear in the first movement and relates them to sound-events that bear similar characteristics and occur in the second movement. We now describe these in more details.

2.2 The “Baby Sounds” and their Categorization

The *baby sounds* appear in the first movement of the composition starting at measure 39. Whether they are “*screams*”, “*cooings*” or “*babbles*”, they all share a set of clearly identifiable characteristics:

- They are played by the violins accompanied by two (transformed and amplified) solo instruments;
- They occur in the high to very high register;
- The dynamic markings are between *ppp* and *mf* following a crescendo-decrescendo overall shape;

- The string parts always include a high proportion of glissandi, often played *tremolo*, with sounds often produced as *harmonics*.

With few exceptions, labels (actually instructions related to the electronic part) appear in the score that indicate the “category” to which the corresponding sound belongs. In accordance with the composition’s underlying metaphor, the first are *baby screams*, the second *baby cooings* and the last are *baby babbles*. They appear, respectively, 6, 4 and 8 times over the course of the movement. Although they are quite clearly distinguishable aurally as pertaining to separate categories their general features as read from the score are very similar and the factors contributing to their differences are far from obvious.

During the second movement, between measures 133 and 190, a series of 30 sound-events can be heard, each of between 1.5 and 4 seconds in duration, which share very similar orchestration, playing modes, register etc. as the *baby sounds* of the first movement. As no real-time transformation is applied at that particular moment of the piece, no label appears alongside their appearance in the score.

The two questions that will provide the main thread through the remainder of this article are as follow: considering elements from the score as well as from the recording of the piece [7] is there a way to identify the differences between the three categories of *baby sounds* that appear in the first movement? Based on this information, is it possible to determine to what kind of baby sounds, if any, the events in the second movement pertain?

3. FEATURES EXTRACTION

3.1 Preliminary Remarks

To tackle these questions, features were extracted from each of the *baby sounds* of the first movement as well as from the “potential” ones of the second movement. Acoustic features, which are often used for genre classification and instrument identification tasks, were calculated directly from the audio excerpts as found in [7]. Symbolic features were calculated using MIDI files obtained from the score *via* its transcription using a music-editing software.

In all the tests performed acoustic and symbolic features were first considered as forming separate data sets before being combined into a single one (which will be called the “comprehensive set”). In all three cases, the quantification not only allowed for computerized treatment but also offered the common ground on which audio and symbolic aspects could be brought together. The following two subsections describe the specific features that have been extracted.

3.2 Audio Features

The acoustic classification process was based on calculating features that not only can describe audio excerpts in a vector space, but also correlate to human perceptual aspects (described below).

To obtain the features for each excerpt, we first divided each audio file in frames of 43ms, multiplied it by a Hanning window and calculated its DFT. Each feature, briefly described below, was calculated for each frame.

- The energy (which is closely related to the loudness) [8], is the sum of the squared absolute values of the samples of a frame.
- The spectral roll-off [8, 9] is the frequency under which 95% of the energy of the signal lies. It gives an idea of the roughness of the sound.
- The spectral flux [9] depicts the spectral difference between the current frame and the previous one. It tends to highlight note onsets and quick spectral variations.
- The pitch [10] is also calculated for every frame. The algorithm used, based on autocorrelation, retrieves the most prominent pitch in the frame. If no pitches are found, the algorithm yields zero.

The mean, variance and the time-domain centroid of each feature are calculated [8, 9] along the frames. At the end of this process, each audio excerpt is described by a 12 dimensional feature-vector. As is shown in works related to audio classification, the Euclidian distance between two vectors tends to be small when the related audio excerpts sound alike [9].

3.3 Symbolic Features

The symbolic features extracted were obtained using the OpenMusic library called SOAL [5, 11]. It allows for the extraction of quantified measures on symbolic (MIDI) data relating to the statistical dimensions such as densities, inharmonicity and relative-range, either considered “a-chronically” (i.e., spatial, vertical or out of time) or “diachronically” (in time). More details about this library can be found in [5].

All the symbolic features extracted here are related to “textural” qualities of the excerpts considered. These were established as the following:

- Virtual-fundamental: gives the “fundamental” note obtained by evaluating the distance between the first two lowest pitches of each excerpt;
- E-deviation in harmonicity: corresponds to the deviation between the file's total pitch-content and the harmonic series deduced from the virtual fundamental.
- Relative density: is obtained by dividing the total number of pitches by the theoretical maximum possible number of them within the total range of the excerpt. A typical chromatic cluster, for instance, would correspond to the maximum relative density.
- Absolute Range: corresponds to the difference between the highest and the lowest note present in the excerpt.
- Relative Range: the range occupation of the excerpt considered with respect to the range spanned by all the excerpts considered. In the case of *Speakings*,

this total range goes from F₄ (or 6500 Midicents) to G#₇ (or 10400 Midicents).

The symbolic features extracted considered each single excerpt a-chronically.

4. CLASSIFICATION AND EXTENSION

The experiments described in this section aimed at obtaining a classification of the features that best represented each of the *baby-sound* categories. For this purpose all data was normalized to zero mean and unity variance, so that all features would be considered with equal weight.

General-purpose computer-based classification processes are frequently based on vector descriptions of data points. They highlight correlations in the data that are usually hard to identify manually. Although such general-purpose algorithms ignore specialist knowledge they have achieved important results in many fields.

Two different algorithms were used and compared: support vector machines (SVM) and C4.5 binary decision trees (BDT).

A SVM is a supervised machine-learning algorithm that yields a classification based on the maximization of a decision margin [12]. Although it has been used to generate efficient classifiers from data, its internal parameters are hard to interpret. SVMs are especially important because of their known ability to find hidden relationships between features [12]. They tend, furthermore, to yield models that generalize well, usually leading to better results in testing data at the expense of a lower performance when the model is executed over the training data.

A BDT is a supervised machine-learning algorithm whose training process consists of selecting features from data that yield an optimal entropy classification [13]. For this reason, the classification model is easy to interpret but, at the same time, may have limited generalization ability. The BDT may reveal decision processes that can be hard to obtain manually but, crucially in the present context, are easy to interpret [13].

4.1 The Classification of the Baby Sounds in the 1st Movement

In a first experiment both algorithms were trained using the labeled data from the first movement and the resulting systems applied to the classification of that same training data. This test aimed at detecting if the features made sense for classification. The accuracy of this process is shown in Table 1.

Number (and %) of correctly classified baby sounds	SVM	BDT
Audio	14 (77%)	17 (94%)
Symbolic	11 (61%)	14 (77%)
Comprehensive	15 (83%)	17 (94%)

Table 1. Classifications of the Baby Sounds in the first movement.

We note that the results obtained by the SVM are notably worse than those obtained by the BDT, in spite of the former being a more sophisticated model. This, however, is in line with the fact that its training process aims at optimizing the *generalization* capability of the system. The BDT, on the other hand, maximizes its results considering the training data alone.

Furthermore, the BDTs training process showed the most discriminative features in both sets. In the symbolic features set, the algorithm selected the relative density and the relative occupation while in the acoustic set as well as in the comprehensive set, it selected the average energy, the average spectral flow and the average spectral roll-off.

4.2 Extension to the Second Movement

The systems resulting from the training of both algorithms were then used to determine the category to which the *baby sounds* that appear in the second movement could be said to belong to. The results are shown in Table 2.

	Binary Decision Tree				Support Vector Machine		
	Symb.	Symb. 2	Audio	Comp.	Symb.	Audio	Comp.
1	B	B	C	C	B	C	B
2	B	C	S	S	B	B	B
3	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
4	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
5	B	C	C	C	B	B	B
6	C	B	S	S	B	B	B
7	B	C	C	C	B	B	B
8	B	C	S	S	B	B	B
9	B	B	C	C	B	B	B
10	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
11	B	B	B	B	B	B	B
12	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
13	B	B	B	B	B	C	B
14	B	B	S	S	B	C	B
15	B	B	S	S	B	C	B
16	B	B	C	C	B	C	B
17	S	B	S	S	B	B	B
18	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
19	B	B	C	C	B	B	B
20	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
21	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
22	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
23	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
24	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
25	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
26	B	B	C	C	B	B	B
27	C	C	S	S	B	B	B
28	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
29	S	B	S	S	B	B	B
30	B	B	S	S	B	B	B
S	2	0	21	21	0	0	0
C	2	5	7	7	0	5	0
B	26	25	2	2	30	25	30
S	6,67%	0,00%	70,00%	70,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
C	6,67%	16,67%	23,33%	23,33%	0,00%	16,67%	0,00%
B	86,67%	83,33%	6,67%	6,67%	100,00%	83,33%	100,00%

Table 2. Classifications of the Baby Sounds in Second movement.

Although data from the second movement is not labeled (no ground-truth is provided) it can be observed that the results of most executions are consistent between themselves. This means that, considering the specific features selected (both acoustic and symbolic), the sound events of the second movement are closer to the first move-

ment’s *baby babbles* than to the others baby sounds. Since this is true for all three feature-sets, it is important to discuss this result more thoroughly.

The classification of excerpts of the second movement, using the BDT only matched the results yielded by the SVMs when symbolic features were considered. This is to be expected, as the auditory similarity depends on the correlations between acoustic features, while symbolic features are meaningful even if analyzed individually.

The BDT decision process considered only two features from the symbolic dataset: Relative Range and Relative Density. In order to explore the combinations further, these two features were removed from the set and a new learning process initiated. The remaining features formed the “Symbolic 2” set. When training was based on this set, the algorithm considered two further features: E-harmonic Deviation and Relative Range.

The results in the second movement, shown in Table 2, are consistent with the ones obtained previously with a clear prominence of *baby babble* sounds.

5. DISCUSSION

Looking back at the music analytical questions formulated at the beginning of this article the results may now be interpreted within the “*basic metaphor*” underlying the composition. Leaving aside all considerations about what the composer’s actual interpretation has been, the “reminders” of the *baby sounds* that precede the process leading to the “mantra” can be argued to correspond to the last of the three types of baby sounds. Remaining at the metaphorical level, the *baby babbling*, albeit in a more discreet form, become part of the “frantic chatter” through which the music – and the speech consciousness – evolves until reaching its final “serenity”.

Such an observation, of course, does not in itself constitute an analysis of the composition. How it would fit into a more extensive study of the work would also greatly depend on the particular angle taken in such an endeavor. The results to be underlined here have more to do with the method employed and, in particular, with the dual role the computer played in reaching our conclusion.

The first of these roles is to be found in the increase in precision and in the associated extension in the number of “parameters” that can be taken into consideration in the analytical process. As a correlate, the quantification process that underlies these new possibilities offers a more objective basis for discussion and for communication of results.

The second role played by the computer is more obvious: namely in systematization of the exploration of these parameters. In this context, the fundamental difference between the two algorithms should be stressed again. The SVM generalizes user-labeled data but does so without providing any feedback as to the reasons that underlie its decisions. The BDT, on the other hand, provides an explicit hierarchy of features that can be discussed independently and may become the basis of a new set of experiments.

In both cases, the results provided by the algorithms depend, in two distinct senses, on the particular features that have been extracted. First, at the algorithmic level, a

poor selection of features may lead to unsatisfactory classification. Second, at the analytical level, the same may weaken the interpretability of the results or their meaningfulness.

In the analysis presented here questions of segmentation and categorization were directly suggested by information provided by the composer. In a more general context, such data would have to be obtained from other sources, including independent (music) analytical decisions. Questions of identity and similarity, however, are bound to arise in a variety of contexts. In the face of the increasing complexity of a certain type of repertoire, the help of computerized processes such as the ones described here are likely to become increasingly important.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The computer-based music analytical approach proposed here, albeit still being in its preliminary stages, provided concrete support in tackling musical repertoire in which both written and recorded sources are best considered in tandem.

None of the features extracted was obtained by a method new to either the field of music information retrieval or to that of music analysis *per se*. Their handling, however, opened the way for a more comprehensive approach, in which information obtained from different sources could be considered simultaneously. The use of the machine learning techniques also showed the computer's potential as a tool to explore and make sense of the multiplicity of data that such an approach implies.

Amongst the tasks envisioned in the future are: the elaboration of further analytical examples, more detailed discussions of the methodological issues that may arise from the extension of the method as well as a harmonization of the computational tools involved.

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